

Survey of Medicinal Plants used by Local people of Armori taluka, Gadchiroli District, (M.S.) India

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Abstract :

The current work is based on a thorough field study of medicinal plants conducted in Armori taluka area. Locals in this region rely on the forest flora for their livelihood and on herbal remedies to treat illnesses and disorder. There are 49 reported species of medicinal plants, which belongs to 48 genera and 30 families of the plants used by the local people. Botanical names of all the plants have been arranged alphabetically. Local names, part use and medicinal use have also been provided.

Key words: Documentation, medicinal plants, Armori.

Introduction:

Since the beginning human beings have been coexisted with nature, and plants have been important to their existence as they supply the necessities of life; including food, shelter, medicine, clothing, etc. Our prehistoric forebears were able to use numerous wild plants in diverse parts of the world for their specific use in the process of trial and error. The knowledge on the medicinal plant was transferred from one generation to next generation orally or without any published records. India is rich in ethnobotanical knowledge. The ethnic and rural people of India have preserved a large bulk of traditional knowledge of medicinal use of plants growing around them (Yigra 2010). This knowledge is handed down to generation through word of mouth and extensively used for the treatment of diseases (Mishra *et al.*, 2008). However, there is now a big generational gap between the young and old. As a result, traditional information has not been effectively transferred. Therefore, the present effort was undertaken in order to gather and record the traditional knowledge of the local Medicine Man (*Vaidu*) from Armori taluka (same medicinal

plants used to treat various ailments and disorders).

Materials and Methods:

Field tours were organized frequently to collect the information, many interviews were conducted with old Medicine Man (*Vaidu*) belonging to different categories. As much as 49 different plant species have been surveyed and collected. The collected plant species were identified with the help of floras and processed according to standard method of herbarium preparation. All the specimens are deposited in herbarium of Department of Botany, Mahatma. Gandhi. Arts, Science and Late N. P. Commerce College, Armori.

Results and Discussion:

All 49 species of flowering plants from 48 genera and 30 families were included in the assessment of medicinal plants in the study area. These plants are used to cure a variety of illnesses and diseases, including Cholera, Diabetes, Dysentery, Asthma, Fever, Cough etc. From present study. It is revealed that there is still need to collect information on traditional knowledge which will be helpful for further scientific study on drug formulation and discovery of new drugs.

Table: - List of Ethno-medicinal plant used by local people.

Sr. No.	Botanical Name	Local Name	Part Use	Uses
1.	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Gunj	Leaves	Leaves chewed and juice swallowed in stomatitis.
2.	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.	Khair	Bark	Bleeding gum
3.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Aghada, Kutri	Root	Dog bite, Scorpion bite
4.	<i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i> Medic.	Adulsa	Leaves	Cough and asthma.
5.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr.	Bel	Fruit	Stomachache, leucorrhoea
6.	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Maharuk	Bark	Stomach pain and cholera.
7.	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.f.) wang.	PandhariAkwal	Bark	Stomach pain due to worms
8.	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Bhuineem	Leaves	Malarial fever and

	(Burm.f.) wall. ex Nees			worm's infestation.
9.	Aristolochia indica L.	Aristolochia indica L.	Leaves	Snake bite as an antidote
10.	Asparagus racemosus Willd.	Shatavari, Marbat	Tuberous root	Lactation after delivery, acidity, leucorrhoea weakness and weight gain
11.	Azadirachta indica Juss	Kadu-Neem	Leaves and seed	Used in fever, worm fever and internal body heat. Seed oil is used in scabies.
12.	Bacopa monnieri (L.) Penn.	Brahmi	Leaves	Used for cough and hair falls
13.	Balanites aegyptica (L.) Del.	Hinganbet	Fruit	Food poison.
14.	Baliospermum montanum (Willd.) Muell-Arg	Jamal-gota	Root	Root decoction used for stomach pain due to indigestion.
15.	Bauhinia racemosa Lam.	Apta	Bark	Menstrual irregularity.
16.	Boerhavia diffusa L.	Khaperkhuti	Root	Jaundice
17.	Bombax ceiba L.	Kate-sawar	Bark	Menorrhagia, blood purification.
18.	Boswellia serrata Roxb. ex Colebr.	Salai	Bark	Wound healing.
19.	Butea monosperma (Lam.) Taub.	Palas	Flower & Seed	Flowers used against burning sensation and seed used for urinary problem
20.	Caesalpinia bonduce (L.) Roxb.	Sagargoti	Seed	Menorrhagia, also used for abortion.
21.	Calotropis gigantea (Ait.) R. Br.	Rui	Flower	Asthma and bronchitis.
22.	Cassia fistula L.	Bahava	Pod and root	Pod is used to treat stomach pain
23.	Catharanthus roseus (L.) G. Don.	Jagannath	Leaves	Used to treat diabetes.
24.	Celastrus paniculatus Willd.	Malkanguni	Seed	Seed oil is used for paralysis
25.	Celosia argentea L.	Kombda	Root	Kidney stone.
26.	Chlorophytum tuberosum Bakar	Safedmusali	Tuberous root	Root tubers are used as a tonic.
27.	Costus speciosus (Koen.) J. E. Smith	Kewakanda	Tuber	Used for to treat arthritis.
28.	Cullen corylifolia (L.) Medik.	Bawachi	Seed	Seed oil is used for scabies and skin diseases.
29.	Diplocyclos palmatus (L) Jeddrey.	Shivalingi	Seed	Used to enhance ovulation in woman.
30.	Elephantopus scaber L.	Rantambhaku	Root	Used for bleeding piles.
31.	Emblia officinalis Gaertn	Awala	Fruit	Used for constipation, it is the one the ingredient of triphala churn.
32.	Euphorbia hirta L.	Dudhi	Leaves, stem	Shoot with leaves are used to enhance milk secretion in mothers.
33.	Gymnema sylvestre (Retz.) R. Br. ex Schult.	Gudmar	Leaves	Leaf juice is taken internally to control

				diabetes.
34.	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Muradseng, Atai	Fruit	Fruit paste is given to cure stomachic.
35.	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> (Buch.-Ham.) Wall. ex G. Don	Kuda	Root and stem bark	Stem bark is used for dysentery and root bark is used as a worm infestation
36.	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	Wagnaki	Leaves	Leaf warmed and applied to cure wound.
37.	<i>Maytenus senegalensis</i> (Lam.) Excell.	Bharati	Leaves	Young leaves are chewed and juice spitted out to cures mouth sores.
38.	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.	Kamal	Leaf and seed	Seed with spongy testa is used in worm infestation. Leaf is used for skin diseases.
39.	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Choiv.	UtaranVel	Flower	Flower juice is used in cough.
40.	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum &Thonn.	Bhuiawala	Root	Used to cure jaundice.
41.	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Erandi	Leaf and Seed	Leaf is applied over swelling. Seed oil is used for constipation.
42.	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Oken	Kusum	Stem bark	Stem bark powder is used in dysentery.
43.	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L. f.	Biba	Fruit	Oil is used as an antiseptic, cuts and foot cracks.
44.	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Gorakhmundi	Leaf	Leaf juice is used for toothache, cough and indigestion.
45.	<i>Spilanthus calva</i> DC.	Akkalkara	Flower	Flowers are used to cure cough.
46.	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Behada	Fruit	Fruit powder is used for cough, constipation and indigestion. It is also used in the preparation of triphala powder.
47.	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Hirda	Fruit	Fruit is useful for cough, indigestion, gases, constipation, stomachic. It is also one of the ingredient of triphala powder.
48.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers. ex Hook. &Thoms	Gudvel	Stem	Used in fever, jaundice,
49.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Kambarmodi	Leaf	Fresh leaf used in cuts and wounds.

Conclusion:

All the medicinal plants are harvested from the forest to treat illnesses and other usages, but they are not conserved. Therefore, it is important to raise awareness among traditional practitioners about the need to protect local plant species before their extinction from the area.

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References:

1. Jain S. K. 1987. A manual of Ethnobotany. *Scientific publisher, Jodhpur*, India.
2. Lakshminarshimhan P, Sharma B. D. 2000. Flora of Maharashtra State Dicotyledons, Vol. 1 (Ranunculaceae to Rhizophoraceae). *Botanical Survey of India*.
3. Mishra S. B. Dwedi S, Shasi A. and K. Prajapati 2008. Ethnobotanical uses of some plant species by Ethnic and Rural people of the Salem dist. with special reference to the conservation of vanishing species; *Ethnobotanical leaflet*, 12 : 873-887.
4. Singh N. P., Lakshminarshimhan P, Karthikeyan S, Prasanna 2001. Flora of Maharashtra State Dicotyledons, Vol. 2 (Combretaceae to Rhizophoraceae). *Botanical Survey of India*.
5. Yigra G, 2010. Ethnobotanical Study of Medicinal plants in around Almata, Southern Tigray, northern Ethiopia. *Current Research Journal of Biological Sciences* 2 (5): 338-344.